

Studies on 8-Quinolinol-N-Oxides and Some of Their Metal Chelates†

K. D. GHUGE, P. UMAPATHY* and D. N. SEN

National Chemical Laboratory, Poona-8, (India)

Manuscript received 19 October 1977, revised 26 April 1978, accepted 7 July 1978

Several metal chelates of 8-quinolinol-N-oxide with Cu(II), Be(II), Mn(II), Sn(II), Fe(III), Cr(III), Al(III), Sn(IV), Ti(IV), UO_2^{2+} , VO^{2+} and MoO_4^{2+} and also Cu(II) and Fe(III)/ VO^{2+} chelates of 5-nitro-, 5,7-dinitro- and 5,7-dibromo-8-quinolinol-N-oxide, have been synthesized in pure state. These chelates are characterized by their elemental analyses, I.R., U.V.-visible spectral and magnetic susceptibility data wherever possible. The ligands act as bidentate, o,o chelating agents, co-ordinating through the -NO oxygen and the phenolic hydroxyl oxygen atom. I.R. evidence is provided for the monodentate character of the ligands in Sn(II) and Sn(IV) complexes. Deuteration studies have also been made.

ALTHOUGH 8-quinolinol-N-oxide and some of its substituted derivatives have been extensively used for the extraction and analytical determination of metal ions¹⁻⁴, only the metal complexes of vanadium $VO(OQNO)_2^5$ and molybdenum $MoOCl(OQNO)_2^6$ and $MoOCl(5,7-Br_2-OQNO)_2$, where (HOQNO=8-quinolinol-N-oxide) are isolated in crystalline form. It is considered that the elucidation of the mode of co-ordination of 8-quinolinol-N-oxide and its substituted derivatives would be of interest. In the present study several metal chelates of 8-quinolinol-N-oxide and its substituted derivatives have been synthesized and characterized. The results of our findings are reported here.

Experimental

The ligands, 8-quinolinol-N-oxide and its 5-nitro-, 5,7-dinitro- and 5,7-dibromo-substituted derivatives were prepared according to the procedures described in literature^{7,8}. Anhydrous tin(II) chloride was prepared by dehydration of A.R. grade tin(II) chloride dihydrate, $SnCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$, by reaction with acetic anhydride⁹. Titanium tetraethoxide was prepared according to the reported method¹⁰. All the other chemicals used were of A.R. grade. I.R. spectra in Nujol mull were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer infrared spectrophotometer Model No. 221 equipped with NaCl(CsBr) optics. U.V.-visible spectra in different solvents were recorded on Unicam-SP-500 spectrophotometer. Diffuse reflectance spectra of solid samples were obtained on a Unicam-SP-500 spectrophotometer fitted with the standard reflectance attachment and employing a block of magnesium carbonate as standard. The magnetic susceptibilities were determined at room temperature using the Faraday method with mercuric tetrathiocyanato cobaltate(II) employed as

calibrant. Magnetic moments were calculated by use of the equation

$$\mu_{eff} = 2.84 \sqrt{\chi_M^{O.T.T.} T}$$

The metal chelates were synthesized by following the general procedure outlined below :

Hot solutions of the appropriate metal salt (0.001 mole) and the ligand (0.002 or 0.003 mole) in water-alcohol mixture (1 : 1) were mixed together with stirring. pH of the resulting mixture was adjusted to ~6.5 with dilute ammonia (1 : 4) or saturated sodium acetate solution. (In case of Cr(III) chelate, solid urea *in situ* was used.) The solid that separated out was collected on a filter, washed with alcohol-water mixture and dried. All the compounds were purified by recrystallization from the solvents mentioned in the Table 1. Yields ~80%. Titanium and tin complexes were obtained by refluxing metal tetrachlorides and the ligand solutions in dry benzene for 6 hours.

Results and Discussion

The I.R. spectra of 8-quinolinol-N-oxide in solid and its deuterated analogue (Fig. 1) show multiple medium strong absorption bands over a wide range 3000 cm^{-1} -1750 cm^{-1} . In the solution spectra the band profiles are unaffected by dilution. In addition aromatic CH stretching modes are observed at 3060 cm^{-1} -3010 cm^{-1} . The series of medium strong bands are shifted, on deuteration, and three prominent bands are observed at 2050-1850 cm^{-1} . The absorption pattern observed in the spectra (solid) of 5-nitro-, 5,7-dinitro- and 5,7-dibromo-substituted derivatives of 8-quinolinol-N-oxides is similar. However, previous investigators⁸ reported only a

†NCL Communication No : 2210.

*Author to whom correspondence should be addressed.

TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA OF THE METAL CHELATES OF 8-QUINOLINOL-N-OXIDES

Sl. No.	Compound	M.P. (°C)	Crystallizing solvent	C	H	N	M	μ_{eff}^{***} (B.M.)
				%				
1.	8-Quinolinol-N-Oxide	139	Alcohol	66.56 (67.05) ^a	4.51 (4.38)	8.69 (8.69) ^a		—
2.	5,7-Dibromo-8-quinolinol-N-oxide	203	Glacial acetic acid	33.90 (33.90)	1.50 (1.60)	4.50 (4.50)	—	—
3.	5-Nitro-8-quinolinol-N-oxide	191-3	Alcohol	52.35 (52.43)	3.10 (2.90)	13.50 (13.50)	—	—
4.	5,7-Dinitro-8-quinolinol-N-oxide	231-4	Glacial acetic acid	43.00 (43.00)	1.86 (2.00)	16.80 (16.70)	—	—
5.	Bis-(8-quinolinolato-N-oxide)copper(II)	263	Chloroform	56.58 (56.33)	3.16 (3.15)	7.30 (7.30)	16.58 (16.56)	2.09
6.	Bis-(8-quinolinolato-N-oxide)beryllium(II)	342	—do—	65.78 (65.67)	3.85 (3.67)	8.50 (8.51)	2.70 (2.73)	—
7.	Bis-(8-quinolinolato-N-oxide)manganese(II)	293 (decomp.)	—do—	58.03 (57.63)	3.81 (3.22)	7.40 (7.47)	14.50 (14.64)	3.95
8.	Oxobis-(8-quinolinolato-N-oxide)vanadium(IV)	>370 (decomp.)	—do—	56.07 (55.85)	3.15 (3.12)	7.20 (7.23)	13.05 (13.15)	1.77
9.	Dioxobis-(8-quinolinolato-N-oxide)molybdenum(VI)	280	—do—	—	—	6.21 (6.25)	21.09 (21.40)	—
10.	Dioxobis-(8-quinolinolato-N-oxide)uranium(VI)	282	Methanol	36.52 (36.63)	2.08 (2.05)	4.71 (4.74)	31.99 (40.32)	—
11.	Tris-(8-quinolinolato-N-oxide)chromium(III)	288 (decomp.)	Chloroform	60.58 (60.91)	3.44 (3.41)	7.81 (7.89)	9.70 (9.77)	4.13
12.	Tris-(8-quinolinolato-N-oxide)aluminium(III)	350	—do—	63.70 (63.92)	4.06 (3.57)	8.26 (8.28)	5.30 (5.30)	—
13.	Tris-(8-quinolinolato-N-oxide)iron(III)	270 (decomp.)	—do—	60.40 (60.46)	3.73 (3.38)	7.81 (7.83)	10.40 (10.40)	5.73
14.	Dichlorobis-(8-quinolinol-N-oxide)tin(II)*	356	—	42.34 (42.32)	2.84 (2.76)	5.48 (5.47)	23.16 (23.24)	—
15.	Tetrachlorobis-(8-quinolinol-N-oxide)tin(IV)*	361-2 (decomp.)	—	36.86 (37.09)	2.53 (2.42)	4.78 (4.80)	20.39 (20.37)	—
16.	Dichlorobis-(8-quinolinolato-N-oxide)titanium(IV)*	306 (decomp.)	—	49.45 (49.23)	2.80 (2.76)	6.40 (6.38)	10.80 (10.91)	—
17.	Diethoxybis-(8-quinolinolato-N-oxide)titanium(IV)*	>370 (decomp.)	—	57.38 (57.36)	5.10 (4.84)	6.33 (6.33)	10.40 (10.21)	—
18.	Bis-(5,7-dibromo-8-quinolinolato-N-oxide)copper(II)	234 (decomp.)	Chloroform	30.77 (30.91)	1.19 (1.15)	4.12 (4.15)	9.10 (9.09)	2.01
19.	Oxobis-(5,7-dibromo-8-quinolinolato-N-oxide)vanadium(IV)	>380	—do—	30.95 (30.77)	1.16 (1.15)	4.10 (4.12)	7.21 (7.24)	1.73
20.	Dioxobis-(5,7-dibromo-8-quinolinolato-N-oxide)uranium(VI)	>380	—do—	24.00 (23.87)	1.00 (0.89)	2.95 (3.09)	26.20 (26.29)	—
21.	Bis(5-nitro-8-quinolinolato-N-oxide)copper(II)	273 (decomp.)	—do—	45.13 (45.63)	2.18 (2.18)	11.80 (11.82)	13.40 (13.42)	2.00
22.	Tris-(5-nitro-8-quinolinolato-N-oxide)iron(III)	255 (decomp.)	—do—	48.50 (48.31)	2.30 (2.25)	12.50 (12.52)	8.30 (8.32)	5.80
23.	Bis-(5,7-dinitro-8-quinolinolato-N-oxide)copper(II)	329 (decomp.)	—do—	38.90 (38.35)	1.47 (1.43)	14.86 (14.90)	11.20 (11.27)	2.01
24.	Oxobis-(5,7-dinitro-8-quinolinolato-N-oxide)vanadium(IV)	190 (decomp.)	—do—	38.37 (38.12)	1.45 (1.42)	14.70 (14.81)	8.90 (8.97)	1.74

^a = calculated values.
decomp. = decomposed.

* = purified by repeated digestion with hot benzene.
** = Data were obtained at room temp. 300°K.

broad band at 2857-2440 cm^{-1} in the I.R. spectrum of 8-quinolinol-N-oxide. The absorption features observed in the spectra of 8-quinolinol-N-oxide and in its substituted derivatives point to the presence of a strong intramolecular hydrogen bond involving the hydroxyl hydrogen atom and the N-oxide oxygen atom. The stretching vibration of unbonded OH group appears as a strong absorption band in the 3620 cm^{-1} region. A shift of this band to lower frequencies is accepted as a criterion for the presence of hydrogen bonding. In the solution spectra of 8-quinolinols Badger and Moritz¹¹ observed such a band at ca. 3400-3350 cm^{-1} . The series of deep, broad and medium strong bands observed in N-oxides spectra might arise from Fermi resonance interaction between the hydroxyl stretching band of the strong intramolecular O—H...O

hydrogen bond and the overtone and combination bands of ($\nu_{\text{CO}} + \delta_{\text{O-H}}$) and other fundamental vibrational modes of the molecule.

The complexity of the band structure is simplified in the deuterated spectra due to perhaps the less possible number of ($\nu_{\text{CO}} + \delta_{\text{OD}}$) and (ν_{OD}) interactions. The profiles of hydrogen stretching I.R. bands of molecules with hydrogen bonds in systems, RAH...BR¹ are treated by Bratos¹² recently. It is shown that the band shaping mechanisms are the anharmonic coupling between the AH stretching and different low frequency external motions and the Fermi resonance between states involving the AH stretching and some other internal modes. In cases of weak hydrogen bond, the profile is essentially a broad asymmetrically distorted. Gaussian produced

Fig. 1. IR Spectra in Nujol and H. C. B Mulls of :

- (i) - - - - - 8-quinolinol-N-Oxide, and
 (ii) ——— Deuterated 8-quinolinol-N-Oxide.

by an anharmonic coupling between the high frequency AH str. mode and the perturbed low frequency AH...B stretching mode.

The elemental analyses of the metal chelates of 8-quinolinol-N-oxides along with those of the ligands are given in Table 1. The spectra of the metal chelates, in general, resemble one another closely and differed with the parent ligand spectrum. The strong (medium) intensity bands present in 8-quinolinol-N-oxide at ca. 1525 cm^{-1} , 1270 cm^{-1} and at ca. 880 cm^{-1} can be ascribed to the phenolic OH deformation modes coupled with C-O str. modes, ($\nu_{\text{CO}} + \delta_{\text{OH}}$) and to the out of plane deformation vibration (δ_{OH}) respectively. These bands on deuteration shifted to 1295 cm^{-1} , 1000 cm^{-1} and to 640 cm^{-1} respectively (isotopic ratio ~ 1.27 to 1.3). A few weak additional bands are observed in the deuterated spectrum in the region, 1500-1400 cm^{-1} , corresponding to the shift of OH bands present in the parent compound at ~ 1800 cm^{-1} (overtone region). The absence of the above absorption bands in the spectra of the metal chelates indicates that the proton of the hydroxyl group is replaced by the metal. Free ligand exhibits the N-O str. at ca. 1320 and the N-O bend (coupled probably with CH bending modes) at 820 cm^{-1} . In the spectra of the chelates the ν_{NO} is shifted to lower frequencies by ~ 30 cm^{-1} . The N-O bending mode is not shifted considerably and in some cases appears as a split band. These features are indicative of co-ordination through the N-O oxygen^{13,14}. The bands observed at ca. 1450, 1300, 1150 and 1050 cm^{-1} in the spectra of both ligand and the chelates are characteristic of substituted pyridine ring vibrations¹⁵. The observed strong and broad bands in the region 900-1000 cm^{-1} in the spectra of Be^{2+} , VO_2^{2+} , UO_2^{2+} and MoO_2^{2+} chelates may be ascribed to the metal-oxygen stretching vibrations¹⁶⁻¹⁸. The considerable broadening of these bands may be due to the overlapping of these bands with those of the ligand vibrations. In the spectra of all the metal chelates two intense absorptions at ca. 1050 cm^{-1} and another nearby, at 1020-1040 cm^{-1} are observed. The band at 1050 cm^{-1} is present in about the same position (as in the ligand) in all the spectra of the chelates while the position of the

band at 1020-1040 cm^{-1} changed with change in the metal. The latter may be ascribed to the C-O str. frequency at the $\rightarrow\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{M}$ site¹⁷.

The M-O str. frequencies involving the N-oxide oxygen in the CsBr region at ca. 440-60 cm^{-1} in the chelates of Cu(II), Mn(II), Cr(III), Al(III) and Fe(III) are similar in frequencies to those found for the metal chelates of other N-oxides^{19,20}. In the spectra of Sn(II) and Sn(IV) complexes with 8-quinolinol-N-oxide absorptions due to hydroxyl group are present and only a slight shift of ν_{NO} is observed. In SnCl_2 methyl substituted pyridine N-oxide adducts, however, larger shifts for ν_{NO} are recently reported²¹. The ligand (HOQNO) apparently acts as a monodentate in these tin compounds.

The electronic spectra of 8-quinolinol-N-oxides and their metal complexes may be conveniently divided into three regions: (a) 220-270 nm; (b) 270-350 nm, and (c) 350-500 nm and above. The (a) and (b) regions are characterized by two main peaks due to $\pi-\pi^*$ transitions²² (252 nm, 278 sh) and one $\eta-\pi^*$ transition band at 340-350 nm perhaps associated with NO function of the ligand^{19,23,24}. In nitro-substituted ligands broad intense bands are observed near 350-370 nm. In region (c) are found the metal-to-ligand charge transfer bands as well as some crystal field (d-d) bands. The charge transfer is from metal to ligand as has been suggested previously by Parish et al²⁵. The trivalent metals Fe(III) and Cr(III) have their charge transfer bands at higher energy as expected for metal-to-ligand transitions. The lowest energy M-L charge transfer bands in high spin complexes of Cr(III) and Fe(III) with 8-quinolinol N-oxides may be ascribed to $t_{2g} \rightarrow \pi^*$ and to $e_g \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions respectively²⁵. The chromium complex if assumed to approach octahedral symmetry with three bidentate ligands would have assignments: ~ 580 nm ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$, ~ 420 nm ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$. However, a broad intense band with maxima at 425 nm which trails into visible region (~ 500 nm) is experimentally observed. Similar strong charge transfer interaction

is reported by Carlin²⁶ in metal complexes of pyridine-N-oxides. The analytical and I.R. spectral data and magnetic moments (Table I) for Cr(III) and Fe(III) indicate that these chelates have octahedral geometries. The nature of the magnetic moments values are probably due to distortions from the regular symmetry. The rather broad ν_{NO} in the I.R. spectrum of the Cr(III) complex is indicative of splitting of this band which may be interpreted in terms of symmetry lowering²⁷. The Fe(III) chelates spectra are characteristic of essentially octahedral co-ordinated species in which the Iron(III) is surrounded by six oxygen atoms. The spectra consist of an intense band with maxima at ca. 418 nm. The other weak crystal field bands are not observed. The spectra resemble the Iron(III) substituted pyridine-N-oxide complexes which were assigned octahedral geometry²⁸. The magnetic moments observed experimentally for the tetra-coordinated Cu(II) chelates (2.0-2.09 B.M.) are of little use in determining the structure of the compounds due to small differences predicted between tetrahedral Copper(II)²⁹ and square planar species^{28,30}. Liehr³¹ has predicted that tetrahedral copper(II) should show a transition in the region 5000-7000 cm^{-1} without electronic transitions in the visible region. The spectra of the Copper(II) chelates show broad absorption bands at ca. 420 nm and no absorptions in the near infrared region. The diffuse reflectance spectra of the complexes, however, show bands at 600 nm and a shoulder at 720 nm. Since the spectra are different from those of $[\text{Cu}(\text{TMG})_4](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ ³² and $[\text{Cu}(\text{HMPA})_4](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ ³³ (TMG=tetramethylguanidine and HMPA=hexamethylphosphoramide), believed to be tetrahedral (with possible small distortions), it seems likely that the copper chelates possess analogous slightly distorted square planar structure. Such distorted square planar copper complexes with substituted pyridine-N-oxide have been reported^{28,30,34}.

A broad charge transfer band in Mn(II) chelate is observed at 350 nm. The bidentate nature of the ligand (I.R. evidence) and the observed magnetic moment for the compound suggests a probable square planar structure for the Mn(II) chelate. The predicted magnetic moment for square planar Mn^{2+} is 3.9 B.M.³⁵. The observed magnetic moments for the VO^{2+} chelates fairly agree with the expected value for d³ species. Selbin³⁶ points out that for Vanadyl(IV) complexes, when orbital contribution is completely quenched, expected magnetic moment is 1.73 B.M. Vanadium in vanadyl compounds is either five or six co-ordinated^{37,38} and five co-ordinated compounds have either trigonal bipyramidal or square pyramidal structure, the former usually being preferred³⁹. X-ray diffraction studies showed that $\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2(\text{acacH}=\text{acetylacetone})$ appears to be five co-ordinated with VO^{2+} group perpendicular to the oxygen base of a square pyramid⁴⁰. Donohue⁴¹ assumed for the compound $[\text{VO}(\text{bipyO}_2)_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ ($\text{bipyO}_2=2,2'$ -bipyridine-1,1'-dioxide) from spectral studies a rectangular pyra-

midal structure. In analogy with the above compounds, vanadyl complexes with 8-quinolinol-N-oxides may be assigned a square or rectangular pyramidal structures.

Acknowledgement

One of us (K. D. Ghuge) thanks the C.S.I.R. (New Delhi) for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship.

References

1. A. N. BHAT and B. D. JAIN, *J. Sci. Ind. Res. Sect. B*, 1960, **19**, 16, 295; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **38**, 327.
2. M. N. AL-ZAGOUM and C. G. WARREN, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1969, **31**, 3465.
3. K. RAMAIAH and V. R. SRINIVASAN, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci. Sect.*, 1962, **A55**, 360.
4. R. D. GUPTA, G. S. MANKU, A. N. BHAT and B. D. JAIN, *J. Less Common Metals*, 1969, **18**, 139; *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1970, **23**, 1387; *Talanta*, 1970, **17**, 772; *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1970, **50**, 109.
5. R. L. DUTTA and S. LAHIRY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **41**, 62.
6. B. CHATTERJEE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **50**, 755.
7. R. G. W. HOLLINGSHEAD, "Oxine and its derivatives", Vol. IV, Butterworths Publications Ltd., London, 1956, p. 996.
8. K. RAMAIAH and V. R. SRINIVASAN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1968, **16**, 635.
9. G. BRAUER, "Handbook of Preparative Inorganic Chemistry", Academic Press, New York, 1963, Vol. I, Second Edition, p. 728.
10. D. C. BRADLEY, D. C. HANCOCK and W. WARDLAW, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 2773.
11. G. M. BADGER and A. G. MORITZ, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 3437.
12. S. BRATOS, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1975, **63**, 3499.
13. Y. KAKIUTI, S. KIDA and J. V. QUAGLIANO, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1963, **19**, 201.
14. L. C. NATHAN and R. O. RAGSDALE, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1974, **10**, 177.
15. H. SHINDO, *Pharm. Bull.*, 1957, **5**, 472.
16. R. J. MAGHE and I. MARTIN, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1963, **28**, 366.
17. R. G. CHARLES, H. FREISER, R. FRIEDEL, L. E. HILLIARD and W. D. JOHNSTON, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1956, **8**, 1.
18. M. N. SASTRI and T. P. PRASAD, *Talanta*, 1967, **14**, 481.
19. S. A. BOYD, R. E. KOHRMAN and D. X. WEST, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1976, **38**, 1605.
20. A. N. SPECA, L. S. GELFAND, L. L. PYTLEWSKI, C. OWENS and N. M. KARAYANNIS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1976, **15**, 1493.
21. J. W. KAUFFMAN, D. H. MOOR and R. J. WILLIAMS, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1977, **39**, 1165.
22. K. NAKAMOTO, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1960, **64**, 1420.
23. A. B. P. LEVER, J. LEWIS and R. S. NYHOLM, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 5262.
24. N. HATA, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1958, **31**, 255.
25. W. BYERS, B. FA-CHUN CHOU, A. B. P. LEVER and R. V. PARISH, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **91**, 1329.
26. R. L. CARLIN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 3773.

27. W. BYERS, A. B. P. LEVER and R. V. PARISH, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, **7**, 1835.
28. R. WHYMAN, W. HATFIELD and J. S. PASCHAL, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1967, **1**, 113.
29. B. N. FIGGIS, *Nature*, 1958, **182**, 1568.
30. R. S. DRAGO, J. T. DONOGHUE and D. W. HERLOCKER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 836.
31. A. D. LIEHR, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1960, **64**, 43.
32. R. LONGHI and R. S. DRAGO, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 11.
33. J. T. DONOGHUE and R. S. DRAGO, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, **2**, 1158.
34. N. M. KARAYANNIS, C. M. MIKULSKI, L. L. PYTLEWSKI and M. M. LABES, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1972, **34**, 8139.
35. A. E. MARTELL and M. CALVIN, "Chemistry of the Metal Chelate Compounds" Prentice-Hall, Inc., N. J., 1956, p. 213.
36. J. SELBIN, *Chem. Rev.*, 1965, **65**, 153.
37. M. M. JONES, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 5995.
38. J. SELBIN, L. H. HOLMES, JR. and S. P. MCGLYNN, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1963, **25**, 1359.
39. R. J. GILLESPIE, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1960, **38**, 818.
40. R. P. DODGE, D. H. TEMPLETON and A. ZALKIN, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1961, **35**, 55.
41. S. K. MADAN and A. M. DONOHUE, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1966, **28**, 1303.